

Search for New Anthelmintics: Part I. Synthesis of Quinazol-(3H)-4-one-Mercapto Acetyl-Ureas and Mandelyl Quinazol-(3H)-4-Ones

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A series of N'-[3-aryl-quinazol-(3H)-4-one-2-yl-mercapto acetyl]-N²-aryl ureas and some 2-mandelyl-3-aryl/cyclohexyl-quinazol-(3H)-4-ones have been synthesised and tested for their anthelmintic activity.

IN view of the pronounced anthelmintic activity exhibited by quinazoline derivatives^{1,2}, isothiocyanates³, anthranilic acid derivatives⁴, substituted ureas⁵ and benzoxazinediones⁶, a number of N'-[3-aryl-quinazol-(3H)-4-one-2-yl-mercapto acetyl]-N²-aryl ureas (1) and 2 mandelyl-3-aryl/cyclohexyl-quinazol-(3H)-4-ones (2) reported in this communication have been prepared for ascertaining their activities.

It may be noted that the -NH-CO-CH₂-S-group present in (1) has been observed by Mackie and Misra⁷⁻⁸ to be responsible for anthelmintic activity

in certain compounds like 2,3 dihydro-3-oxobenzothiazine (a) and rhodanine (b)

while 2-mandelyl-3-aryl/cyclohexyl-quinazol-(3H)-4-ones are expected to have broad spectrum anthelmintic activity in analogy with the similar class of compounds.

2-Mercapto-3-aryl-quinazol-(3H)-4-ones were condensed with substituted chloro acetyl-phenyl ureas to give (1) while condensation of 2-mandelyl-3,1-(4H)-benzoxazone with appropriate amine in pyridine afforded (2) as shown in the scheme.

urea and 2-mandelyl-3-(*p*-tolyl)Quinazol-(3H)-4-one (having asterisk mark in the table) were found to be inactive at single oral dose of 250 mg/kg (*in vivo*). Anthelmintic activity of the rest of the compounds is in progress and will be communicated shortly.

TABLE I
N'-[3-aryl-quinazol-(3H)-4-one-2yl-mercapto acetyl]-N²-aryl ureas

Sl. No.	R'	R	M.P. °C	Composition	Nitrogen Calcd.	Analysis% Found
1.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	220	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ SCl	11.33	10.91
2.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	180	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	12.16	12.07
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenetidyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	165	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ SCl	11.02	10.89
*4.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	187	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	11.71	11.81
5.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	181	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ SCl ₂	11.42	12.01
6.	Benzyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	208	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	11.71	11.21

* Melting points are uncorrected. Yield ranges from 60-75%.

Experimental

(I) *Preparation of N'-[3-aryl-quinazol-(3H)-4-one-2-yl mercapto acetyl N²-aryl ureas*: A mixture of 2-mercapto-3-aryl-quinazol-(3H)-4-one (0.01 mole) (prepared in the standard method⁹) chloro acetyl aryl ureas (0.01 mole) (made according to Verdername¹⁰) and anh. potassium carbonate (1 g) in 20 ml of dry acetone was refluxed on a steam bath for 12 hr under anhydrous condition. After the reaction was over, reaction mixture was filtered to remove inorganic impurities and unreacted solid and the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting crude solid was recrystallised from ethanol as white or pale crystals.

(II) *Preparation of 2-Mandelyl-3-aryl/cyclohexyl-quinazol-(3H)-4-ones*: A mixture of 2-mandelyl-3,1-(4H) benzoxazone (0.01 mole) (prepared according to Sammour *et al.*¹¹) and appropriate amine (0.01 mole) in 30 ml of pyridine was refluxed for 6 hr and the reaction mixture was poured in ice cold dil. hydrochloric acid, the solid product that separated was recrystallised from benzene to give 2-mandelyl-3-aryl/cyclohexyl-quinazol-(3H)-4 ones.

Bioassay: On screening against *H. nana* and *N. brasiliensis* infections in mice, two of the synthesised compounds namely N'-[3-(*p*-Chloro phenyl)-Quinazol-(3H)-4-one-2yl-mercapto acetyl]-N²-*o*-tolyl

TABLE 2
2-Mandelyl-3 aryl/cyclohexyl quinazol-(3H)-4-ones.

Sl. no.	R	M.P. °C	Composition	Nitrogen Analysis %	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	Phenyl	96	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.29	8.33
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	8.18	8.38
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	77	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	8.18	7.88
*4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	170	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	8.18	7.91
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	55	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	7.82	7.99
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	90	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	7.82	8.11
7.	<i>o</i> -Phenetidyl	78	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	7.52	7.38
8.	<i>p</i> -Phenetidyl	80	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	7.52	7.12
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	156	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	7.73	7.48
10.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₄	11.26	10.91
11.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy phenyl	90	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	8.13	8.12
12.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxy phenyl	160	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	8.13	8.41
13.	Benzyl	50	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	8.18	7.89
14.	Cyclohexyl	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.38	8.12

Melting points are recorded in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Yield ranges from 40-50%.

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